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Annotation:

This article explores the relationship between language and religion within the field of Uzbek linguistics, emphasizing the role of religion in social life and the distinctive features of religious language. It also analyzes how religious terms are presented in dictionaries by classifying them into Arabic, Persian-Tajik, and Uzbek origins.

Key words: language, religion, Islam, religious lexicon, religious term, semantization.

Lug'atlarda islomiy religionimlar semantizatsiyasi tamoyillari

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Annotatsiya:

Mazkur maqolada o'zbek tilshunosligida til va din o'rtasidagi aloqadorlik masalalari, dinning ijtimoiy hayotimizdagi o'rni, diniy tilning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari kabi masalalar bilan birga lug'atlarda berilgan diniy so'zlarni arabcha, fors-tojikcha, o'zbekcha so'zlar tarzida guruhladik.

Kalit so'zlar: til, din, islom dini, diniy leksika, religionim, semantizatsiya.

It is well known that the earliest data on the scientific study of the Uzbek language can be found in ancient dictionaries related to the field of lexicography. Since the formation of the Uzbek literary language, lexicography has remained a focal point for writers, scholars, and linguists throughout various historical periods. Following the country's independence, this process has significantly intensified, acquiring a distinctly national orientation and becoming a primary subject of scholarly research. This orientation cannot be imagined without religion—especially without Islam [1; 2]. Islam serves as a fundamental element shaping the spiritual and intellectual worldview of the Uzbek people. Therefore, special attention is being paid to the scientific study of religious activity in Uzbek society. In fulfilling this sensitive and socially significant mission of the state, linguistics is also expected to contribute and assert its scholarly voice.

Consequently, numerous academic studies are currently being conducted in our country on the interrelations between language and religion. Although some aspects of religious lexicon have been examined in such studies, the lexicographic features of religious terms—here referred to as religionims—have not yet been the subject of monographic research within Uzbek linguistics. Yet, any thematic-semantic field or group of terms requires a thorough and fundamental investigation. The present work represents an initial study within this particular direction. In the current socio-political climate, where religious issues are becoming increasingly pressing, the need for such research has grown accordingly. It has become one of the most urgent tasks on the agenda of contemporary Uzbek linguistics.

In independent Uzbekistan, the situation in all spheres, including religious freedom, has significantly improved. As has been officially stated: "It is our constant and vital task to further strengthen interethnic harmony and interreligious tolerance." [4] Without a doubt, linguistic research conducted within this framework plays an essential role in achieving this goal. Thus, one of the pressing issues facing modern Uzbek linguistics is the exploration of how religious vocabulary is reflected in lexicographic sources.

Islamic religious terms (religionims) have, over the centuries, expanded in usage and have come to reflect the spiritual beliefs of the Uzbek people. These terms have moved beyond the bounds of specialized vocabulary and entered into common usage. Therefore, in our view, it is no longer appropriate to describe them as a restricted lexicon. Over the course of millennia, religionims have been employed widely and have become part of the collective linguistic heritage of the people, forming what may be called the "national vocabulary."

The term semantization is borrowed from English and refers to the processes of understanding, interpreting, or uncovering meaning [3].

There are observable differences between religious vocabulary and general-use vocabulary. In general-use vocabulary, synonymy is often accompanied by expressiveness and emotional coloring. Within synonymic paradigms, one term typically serves as the dominant, stylistically neutral representative. However, in religious vocabulary—particularly in the case of religionims—these phenomena are far less active. Within a single language (for instance, Uzbek), synonymy among religionims is extremely inactive. The synonymous terms in such paradigms often originate from different languages and represent lexical borrowings that entered Uzbek at particular stages in its linguistic development. For example, the synonymous words *kalom* (from Arabic), *gap* (from Persian-Tajik), and *jumla* (of native Uzbek origin) exemplify this phenomenon.

In our research, we classified religious terms found in dictionaries according to their linguistic origins—Arabic, Persian-Tajik, and Uzbek.

In the Word of Allah, the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) is referred to by various names and attributes. Based on the exegeses *Mawahib-i 'Aliyya* by Husayn Va'iz Kashifi, *Kashf al-Asrar* by Khwaja Abdullah Ansari, and *The Translation of the Meanings of the Noble Qur'an* by Abdulaziz Mansur, we identified the following names and attributes associated with the Prophet (peace be upon him):

Ahmad – Surah As-Saff, verse 6

Muhammad – Surah Aali 'Imran, verse 144; Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 40; Surah Muhammad, verse 2; Surah Al-Fath, verse 29

Shahid (Witness on the Day of Judgment) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 45

Mubashshir (Bearer of glad tidings about Paradise) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 45

Nadhir (Warner of Hellfire) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 45

Da'iy (Caller to Allah) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 46

Sirajun Munir (Luminous Lamp, Guide) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 46

No	In Arab	In Persian-Tajik	In Uzbek
1	Alloh	Xudo	Tengri
2	Sahar	Bomdod	Tongotar
3	Dahriy	Xudosiz	Dinsiz
4	Salot	Namoz	-
5	Dor ul-baqo	Oxirat	Abadiy makon
6	Dor ul-fano	Foniy dunyo	O'tkinchi makon
7	Duo	Iltijo	Chaqirish, so'rash
9	Do'zax	Jahannam	-
10	Jannat	Behisht	Bo'ston
11	Jamoat	Guruh	Ko'pchilik
12	Janoza	-	To'sish
13	Zunnor	-	Belbog'
14	Izdihom	-	Yig'ilish
15	Ishq	Muhabbat	Sevgi
16	Lafz, Kalima	-	So'z
17	Kalom	Gap	Nutq, jumla
18	Kofir	-	Dinsiz
19	Laylatul qadr	-	Qadr kechasi
20	Lahad	Go'r	Qabr
21	Mavlid	Tavallud	Tug'ilish
22	Madina	Shahar	-
23	Makkai mukarrama	-	Makka
24	Makruh	nodurust	Nomaqbul
25	Mehrob	-	Sajdagoh
26	Rasul, Nabiy	Payg'ambar	Elchi
27	Alloh	Parvardigor, Xudo	Tengri, Tangri
28	Sayyid	-	Janob
29	Ta'ziya	-	Hamdardlik
30	Tobeinlar	-	Izdoshlar
31	Umra	-	Ziyorat
32	Malak	Farishta	-
33	Fatvo	-	Hukm, Qaror
34	Qalb	Ko'ngil	Yurak
35	Qur'on	-	O'quv
36	Hadis	-	Rivoyat
37	Haj	Ziyorat	Qasd qilish
38	Hilol	-	Yangi oy
39	Hisob	-	Sanash
40	Marhum	-	O'tgan

Khatam (Seal of the Prophets) – Surah Al-Ahzab, verse 40
 Munzir (Warner) – Surah Ar-Ra'd, verse 72
 Hadi (Guide to the straight path) – Surah Ar-Ra'd, verse 72
 Shahid (Witness for all nations) – Surah An-Nisa', verse 41
 Burhan (Proof) – Surah An-Nisa', verse 174
 Ra'uf (Kind to the believers) – Surah At-Tawbah, verse 128
 Rahim (Merciful to the believers) – Surah At-Tawbah, verse 128
 Nur (Light) – Surah Al-Ma'idah, verse 15
 Mubin (Clear, without ambiguity) – Surah Az-Zukhruf, verse 29
 Waliyy (Friend of Allah) – Surah An-Nisa', verse 75
 Nasir (Helper of Allah) – Surah An-Nisa', verse 75
 Muzzammil (Wrapped in garments) – Surah Al-Muzzammil, verse 1
 Muddathir (Clothed or covered) – Surah Al-Muddathir, verse 1
 Mudhakkir (Reminder) – Surah Al-Muddathir, verse 21
 Haq (Truth, sincerity) – Surah Yunus, verse 108
 Awwal (The foremost in submission to Allah) – Surah Al-An'am, verse 53
 Ummi (Unlettered) – Surah Al-A'raf, verse 158
 Bashar (Human being) – Surah Fussilat, verse 6
 Sajid (One who prostrates) – Surah Al-Hijr, verse 98
 Mursal (Messenger) – Surah Ya-Sin, verse 3
 Ta-Ha (Purified and Guide) – Surah Ta-Ha, verse 1
 Najm (Star) – Surah An-Najm, verse 1
 Rahmatan li-l-'Alamin (Mercy to all worlds) – Surah Al-Anbiya', verse 107
 Bayyina (Clear Evidence) – Surah Al-Bayyina, verse 1
 Harith (Eager and devoted) – Surah At-Tawbah, verse 128
 Shakir (Grateful) – Surah Al-An'am, verse 53
 Ya-Sin (O noble master) – Surah Ya-Sin, verse 1

All of these names and attributes are mentioned in the Qur'an and are, without exception, of Arabic origin. In the Uzbek language, the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) is referred to by several honorific titles and expressions, such as So'nggi Payg'ambar (The Last Prophet), Allohning elchisi (Messenger of Allah), Rasul, Rasuli Akram (The Noble Messenger), Rasululloh, Sayyidi Olam (Master of the Universe), Sallollohu alayhi va sallam (Peace and blessings be upon him), Sarvari Koinot (Leader of the Universe), and Xayrul Bashar (Best of Mankind).

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